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Leishmania infection silences the interferon system in monocytes.

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We studied parasite infection using RNA-sequencing and primary human culture systems. *Leishmania braziliensis* infection silenced all interferon stimulated gene expression save for the interferon developmentally regulated gene *Ifrd2* and weak activation of *Irf1*. *Leishmania* activated production of *CCL2* and *CXCL8*. *Tlr7* and *MEFV* were both completely silenced following *Leishmania* infection of the monocyte. V-set immunoregulatory receptor *Vsir* was similarly silenced by *L. braziliensis* infection. *L. braziliensis* infection silences the interferon system in monocytes and disables key pattern recognition receptors in the innate immune system.

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